

ANTH-170-03 Written in Bone: Using Human Skeletons to Understand the Ancient Past

Time: Monday and Wednesday, 10:30–11:45 am
Location: BH 101
Email: jessicabeck@vassar.edu
Office Hours: Wednesday 12:45–2:45 pm
Office: BH 312

TV Terror by Santiago Caruso

Since the earliest days of archaeology, scholars and the general public have been fascinated by skeletons recovered from ancient sites. However, human remains are more than a physical bridge between the present and a romanticized past—they also encode valuable information about the identities and daily lives of past peoples. Bioarchaeology is the study of human skeletal remains from archaeological sites. This course will draw upon bioarchaeological case studies from multiple regions and time periods to explore the ways in which researchers use skeletal data to deepen our understanding of ancient lives, while also critically evaluating how such discoveries are portrayed by the popular media.

In class discussions and written assignments, students will engage with debates about how past peoples treated their dead, conceived of personhood, experienced violence and disease, and organized their communities. Over the course of the seminar, students will learn how to formulate clear arguments, draw upon scientific evidence, and develop strategies for writing and revising academic papers. Class time will also be devoted to developing key writing and research skills, such as structuring academic papers, identifying appropriate sources, and interpreting and responding to feedback. Overall, this course will introduce students to the ways in which bioarchaeologists collect evidence from human skeletons to better understand the lived experiences of past individuals and communities.

Learning Outcomes

First-Year Writing Seminar (from the VCWC)

- **Formulating an Argument:** Participate in a scholarly conversation by crafting a paper with a clear, well-organized argument and establishing its relevance to the intended audience.
- **Marshalling Evidence:** Identify, evaluate, and accurately represent an understanding of primary and secondary source materials (g. summary, paraphrase, quotation) and show the relevance of those materials to their own arguments.
- **Writing as Process:** Engage various strategies for using writing to analyze and develop their ideas (free-writing, idea-mapping, reverse-outlining, revising, etc.).
- **Academic Integrity:** Distinguish between plagiarism and the responsible use of sources and cite according to disciplinary conventions.
- **Mechanics and Usage:** Formulate their ideas in clear and cogent prose while adhering to rules of grammatical correctness

ANTH-170-03

- Explain how bioarchaeologists collect data in order to learn about people in the past
- Compare the similarities and differences between life in the prehistoric past and life in the present
- Critically evaluate how bioarchaeological research is received in the media and popular culture
- Formulate a bioarchaeological research question and review multiple lines of academic evidence in order to answer the question

Readings

All assigned readings, news articles and blog posts will be posted as pdfs on Moodle.

Grading

Your grade will be based on four components:

Attendance and participation (30%)	Activity / Lab Responses (10 %)
Short writing assignments (30%)	Final Research Paper and Presentation (30%)

Grading Structure

Attendance and participation (30%): Every week an attendance sheet will circulate that you are required to sign. It is your responsibility to sign the attendance sheet. If you are not able to do so at the beginning of class, you are responsible for asking for the attendance sheet at the end of class. Full attendance for all 27 sessions of the course will guarantee 15% of this attendance grade (0.5% per class). You are allowed one unexcused absence which will not alter your final grade.

However, simply showing up to class is not sufficient to achieve the full 30%. Focused participation in labs or activities, and active participation in group discussions will comprise the remaining 15% of this mark. You will also need to schedule one individual conference with me after Week 7 (after Wednesday, October 16) in order to discuss your final paper and your experience in the class thus far. This will count towards your participation grade.

Short Writing Assignments (30%): This course will incorporate two short writing assignments that are 5–7 pages in length. Each initial draft of the writing assignment will be worth 5% of your grade, and you will revise it and incorporate the feedback of your instructor and/or peers for the final 10% of your grade.

Activity and Lab Responses (10%): These responses will outline specific tasks (e.g. estimate the sex of this mandible), or as areas of reflection or critical analysis about what you have learned (e.g. What are some potential problems with the strategies bioarchaeologists use to estimate sex? How is contemporary material culture used to communicate identity?). Response sheets from the preceding week will be due the next day that class meets. Occasionally these may incorporate a short amount of writing

Final Research Paper (30%): The final research paper will have both a written and a presentation component. The written component will consist of a short 1–2 page project proposal that will be used to develop a 10–12 page research paper that focuses on a bioarchaeological topic of your choice and cites appropriate academic sources. Your topic must be drawn from one of the main categories that will be presented to you during the fifth week of class. You will need to choose a specific project topic and write your short project proposal by Wednesday, October 16 (the last class before fall break), which will be worth 5% of your grade. Your final paper will be worth 20% of your final grade. It should draw from, and properly cite, peer-reviewed books and articles, using data outlined in these sources to present a central argument and critically evaluate the research that has been conducted on the topic thus far.

During the final week of class, you will prepare a short presentation that summarizes your research for your peers. This final project presentation will be worth 5% of the final grade.

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during labs and activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets, written assignments, and final presentations, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Vassar academic policy. You can read the guidelines on Integrity of Academic Work in the Vassar College Regulations available online here: <https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/college-regulations/VassarCollegeRegulations.pdf>

Vassar College Writing Center

You are encouraged to visit the VCWC at least once over the course of this class in order to receive feedback and advice on your FWS writing assignments.

“The Writing Center provides all Vassar students with a community of experienced peer-readers and writers by offering free, one-to-one consultations at any stage of the writing process—from generating a thesis and structuring an argument to fine-tuning a draft. All students are invited to bring writing projects to the Center, including academic essays from any disciplines, lab reports, creative writing, senior theses, and fellowship statements, as well as resumes, cover letters, and CVs. Students can also bring speaking assignments, including oral and multimedia presentations, poster talks, and teaching plans for leading class discussion.”

More information: <https://ltrc.vassar.edu/writing-center/>

Hours: Sundays -Thursdays: 3:00-11:00pm

Appointments: Make appointments online at <https://vassar.mywconline.com/>

Location: Thompson Memorial Library (Main Library) in Room 122,

Written in Bone: Deadlines for Writing Assignments

Date	Assignment	% Final Grade
Wednesday, 9 October 2019	Short Writing Assignment 1: Draft	5%
Wednesday, 16 October 2019	Final Research Paper Proposal	5%
Wednesday, 6 November 2019	Short Writing Assignment 1: Final	10%
Monday, 18 November 2019	Short Writing Assignment 2: Draft	5%
Monday, 02 December 2019	Short Writing Assignment 2: Final	10%
Mon. 9–Wed 11 December 2019	Final Research Paper Presentations	5%
Wednesday, 11 December 2019	Final Research Paper	20%

Please note that after Week 7 (25 October 2019), you must schedule at least one individual conference with Dr. Beck.

COURSE SCHEDULE

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the lecture, discussion, and activities. I reserve the right to change the readings if I feel it is pertinent to the direction of the course, though in this event readings would be exchanged, rather than added.

Week 1: Introduction Life, the Universe, and Everything¹

Wednesday September 4

- **Lecture:** Introduction to course, instructor, and syllabus
- **Activity:** Spotting skeletons

Week 2: Building Skeletons – Introduction to Bioarchaeology & the Basics of Skeletal Biology

Monday September 9

- **Readings:** Agarwal 2012; Martin and Harrod 2012
- **Optional Reading:** Beck 2014
- **Lecture:** Introduction to bioarchaeology, anatomical terminology, and respectful handling of human remains

Wednesday September 11

- **Readings:** White and Folkens 2000, Ch. 2
- **Lecture:** The basic biology of human bone and teeth
- **Activity:** Anatomical terminology review

Week 3: Assessing Sex from Human Skeletal Remains

Monday September 16

- **Readings:** White 2012, Ch. 18, 408–421
- **Lecture:** How bioarchaeologists estimate sex

Wednesday September 18

- **Readings:** Walker and Cook 1998; Stone 2012a
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Sex vs. gender and the implications for bioarchaeology
- **Activity:** Assessing sex

¹ ANTH-170-03

Week 4: Gender in Ancient Societies

Monday September 23

- **Readings:** Robb and Harris 2018
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Approaches to understanding gender in past societies
- **Activity:** Breaking down a complex academic reading

Wednesday September 25

- **Readings:** Davis-Kimball and Behan 2002 (Ch.3–Ch.4)
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Bioarchaeology and insights into gender
- **Activity:** The innominate in depth

Week 5: Estimating the Age of Human Skeletons + Writing Workshop 1

Monday September 30

- **Readings:** Scheuer and Black 2004, Ch.1
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Estimating the age of skeletons
- **Activity:** Estimating age

Wednesday October 2

- **Readings:** Edwards et al., 2016; Graff and Berkenstein 2006; Lieberman 2019
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Writing Workshop I + Presentation of Research Paper Topics

Week 6: Age and Social Identity in the Ancient Past

Monday October 7

- **Readings:** Kamp 2001; Oxenham 2012
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Children and childhood in the past

Wednesday October 9

- **Readings:** Waterman and Thomas 2011
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Age and mortuary practices
- **Activity:** Interpreting grave goods

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 1 DRAFT DUE

Week 7: Violence and Trauma

Monday October 14

- **Readings:** Walker 2001; Perez 2012
- **Lecture and Discussion:** The bioarchaeology of trauma + finding academic sources

Wednesday October 16:

- **Readings:** Stone 2012b; Osterholtz and Martin 2012
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Violence in the past and present
- **Activity:** Trauma lab

FINAL RESEARCH PAPER PROPOSAL DUE

FALL BREAK: OCTOBER 19–OCTOBER 26

Week 8: Health and Disease + Writing Workshop 2

Monday October 28

- **Readings:** Tilley 2012; Zuckerman 2012; Robbins Schug 2016
- **Lecture and Discussion:** The bioarchaeology of disease

Wednesday October 30

- **Readings:** Savage and Yeh 2019
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Writing Workshop II
- **Activity:** Reverse outlining Short Writing Assignment 1

Week 9: Diet

Monday November 4

- **Readings:** Tykot 2006; Larsen 2011 (p.418-419); Hollands 2017 (cartoon)
- **Video:** Christina Warinner “Debunking the Paleo Diet” ([Link](#))
- **Lecture and Discussion:** How bioarchaeologists evaluate ancient diets

Wednesday November 6

- **Readings:** Diamond 1987; Larsen 2006
- **Lecture and Discussion:** The transition to agriculture: biocultural implications
- **Activity:** Modern diets

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 1 FINAL DUE

Week 10: Mobility

Monday November 11

- **Readings:** Bentley 2006; Tung 2012
- **Lecture and Discussion:** How bioarchaeologists assess mobility

Wednesday November 14

- **Readings:** Tung and Knudson 2011
- **Lecture and Discussion:** What did it mean to be a “local” in prehistory?
- **Activity:** Mobility on Vassar campus

Week 11: Mortuary Treatment

Monday November 18

- **Lecture and Discussion:** Placing the Dead: An Introduction to Mortuary Archaeology
- **Readings:** Parker Pearson 2009, Ch. 6, pp.124–140
- **Activity:** Brainstorm for Cemetery Prep

Wednesday November 20

- **Activity:** Calvary Cemetery visit
- **Readings:** Hijaya 1983

Week 12: The Politics of Dead Bodies

Monday November 25

- **Lecture and Discussion:** Recap of Cemetery Visit + Ötzi, Richard III, and other famous skeletons
- **Readings:** Robb 2009; Williams 2015

Wednesday November 27

- **Lecture:** The legislation and display of human remains
- **Q&A Session:** Dr Beisaw on Repatriation
- **Readings:** Beck 2013; Scientific American 2012; Riding In 2004

THANKSGIVING BREAK: NOVEMBER 28–DECEMBER 1

Week 13: Bioarchaeology and the Media

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 2 FINAL DUE

Monday December 2

- **Activity:** Bioarchaeology and the Media Case Studies
- **Discussion:** Bioarchaeology and the Media
- **Readings:** Stojanowski and Duncan 2014

Wednesday December 4

- First round of final project presentations

Week 14: Final Project Presentations

Monday December 9

- Second round of final project presentations
- **LAST DAY OF CLASS**

STUDY PERIOD: DECEMBER 12–DECEMBER 15

READINGS

Agarwal, S. C. (2012). A bioarchaeology of social identity. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(2), 29-31.

Beck, J. (2014, November 25). “There’s something the dead are keeping back”: Why I study bioarchaeology. [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://bonebroke.org/2014/11/25/theres-something-the-dead-are-keeping-back-why-i-study-bioarchaeology/>

Bentley, R.A. (2006). Strontium isotopes from the Earth to the archaeological skeleton: A review. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, 13(3), 135-187.
doi:10.1007/s10816-006-9009-x

Davis-Kimball, J., & Behan, M. (2003). *Warrior women: An archaeologist’s search for history’s hidden heroines*. New York, NY: Time Warner.

Diamond, J. (1987). The worst mistake in the history of the human race. *Discover*, 91–93.

Graff, G, & C. Birkenstein. (2006). *“They Say/I Say”*: *The Moves That Matter in Academic Writing*. New York, NY: W.W. Norton & Company.

Hijiya, J.A. (1983). American gravestones and attitudes toward death: A brief history. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society*, 127(5), 339-363.

Hollands, C. (2017). Profile: Christina Warinner. *Anthropology News*, 58(5): e123-125.
doi: 10.1111/AN.607

Kamp, K. A. (2001). Where Have All the Children Gone?: The Archaeology of Childhood. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, 8(1), 1–34.

Larsen, C.S. (2006). The agricultural revolution as environmental catastrophe: Implications for health and lifestyle in the Holocene. *Quaternary International*, 150, 12-20.
doi: 10.1016/j.quaint.2006.01.004

Larsen, C.S. (2011). *Our origins: Discovering physical anthropology* (2nd ed.). New York, NY: W.W. Norton & Company.

- Martin, D. L., & Harrod, R.P. (2012). New directions in bioarchaeology. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(2): 31-44.
- Martin, D., & Osterholtz, A. (2012). A bioarchaeology of captivity, slavery, bondage, and torture. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(3), 32-34.
- Oxenham, M. F. (2012). Kids through adult eyes: The bioarchaeology of children. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(2), 35-37.
- Parker Pearson, M. (2009). Placing the dead. In *The archaeology of death and burial* (pp. 124-141). Stroud, UK: The History Press.
- Pérez, V.R. (2012). The bioarchaeology of violence. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(3), 35-38.
- Riding In, J. (2005). Decolonizing NAGPRA. In W.A. Wilson & M. Yellow Bird (Eds.) *For Indigenous Eyes Only: A Decolonization Handbook* (pp. 53–66). Santa Fe, NM: School of American Research.
- Robb, J. (2009). Towards a critical Ötziography: Inventing prehistoric bodies. In H. Lambert & M. McDonald (Eds.), *Social bodies*, (pp.100-128). New York, NY: Berghan Books.
- Robb, J., & Harris, O.J.T. (2018). Becoming gendered in European prehistory: Was Neolithic gender fundamentally different? *American Antiquity*, 83(1), 128-147. doi:10.1017/aaq.2017.54
- Robbins Schug, G. (2016). Begotten of corruption? Bioarchaeology and ‘othering’ of leprosy in South Asia. *International Journal of Paleopathology*, 15, 1-9. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpp.2016.09.002
- Savage, Van, and Pamela Yeh. 2019. “Tips from a Pulitzer Prizewinner.” *NATURE* 574: 441–42.
- Scientific American Editors. (2012). Who Owns the Past? *Scientific American*. Access online: <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/who-owns-the-past/>
- Stojanowski, C.M., & Duncan, W.N. (2015). Engaging bodies in the public imagination: Bioarchaeology as social science, science, and humanities. *American Journal of Human Biology*, 27(1): 51-60. doi:10.1002/ajhb.22522.
- Stone, P.K. (2012a). A bioarchaeology of sex and gender: What is the difference and why is it important? *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(2), 38-40.
- Stone, P.K. (2012b). Binding women: Ethnology, skeletal deformations, and violence against Women. *International Journal of Paleopathology*, 2(2-3), 53-60. doi:10.1016/j.ijpp.2012.09.008

- Tilley, L. (2012). The bioarchaeology of care. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(3), 39-41.
- Tung, T. (2012). The bioarchaeology of migration. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(3), 42-45.
- Tung, T. A., & Knudson, K. J. (2011). Identifying locals, migrants, and captives in the Wari heartland: A bioarchaeological and biogeochemical study of human remains from Conchopata, Peru. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 30(3), 247-261. doi: 10.1016/j.jaa.2011.06.005
- Tykot, R.H. (2006). Isotope analyses and the histories of maize. In J.E. Staller, R.H. Tykot, & B.F. Benz (Eds.), *Histories of maize: Multidisciplinary approaches to the prehistory, linguistics, biogeography, domestication, and evolution of maize* (pp. 131-142). Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier Academic Press.
- Edwards, R., Schultz, M., Bucher, D., & Bradley, D.T. (2016). *Going to the Source: A Guide to Academic Integrity and Attribution at Vassar College*. Available online: <https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/sources/VassarGoingToTheSource.pdf>
- Waterman, A.J., & Thomas, J.T. (2011). When the bough breaks: Childhood mortality and burial practice in Late Neolithic Atlantic Europe. *Oxford Journal of Archaeology*, 30(2), 165-183. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-0092.2011.00363.x
- Walker, P. L. (2001). A bioarchaeological perspective on the history of violence. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 30, 573-596. doi: 10.1146/annurev.anthro.30.1.573
- Walker, P.L., & Collins Cook, D. (1998). Gender and sex: Vive la difference. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology*, 106(2), 255-259. doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1096-8644(199806)106:2<255::AID-AJPA11>3.0.CO;2-#
- White, T., & Folkens, P. (2000). *Human Osteology* (2nd ed.). San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- White, T., & Folkens, P. (2012). *Human Osteology* (3rd ed.). San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- Williams, H. (2013, September 28). What is truly wrong about digging up Richard III. [Blog post]. Retrieve from <https://howardwilliamsblog.wordpress.com/2013/09/28/what-is-truly-wrong-about-digging-up-richard-iii/>
- Zuckerman, M.K. (2012). The bioarchaeology of disease. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 12(2), 41-43.